

ASSESSING THE CAPABILITY OF COAST GUARD DISTRICT CENTRAL VISAYAS IN MARITIME SEARCH AND RESCUE OPERATIONS

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ABSTRACT

This study examines the capability of the Coast Guard District Central Visayas in conducting maritime search and rescue operations, focusing on personnel capability, training, operations, assets, and policies and standards. The findings from the demographic and professional analysis reveal a diverse workforce composition. The age distribution shows a mix of early-career professionals and experienced personnel, with a notable male majority (92%). The rank distribution indicates a structured hierarchy essential for effective management. Most personnel hold college degrees, highlighting the emphasis on educational attainment. Years of service show a balanced mix of new talent and experienced staff, with strategic geographical distribution aligning with operational priorities. Respondents' performance in SAR scenarios reveals a readiness to deploy resources swiftly, coordinate with relevant authorities, and utilize specialized assistance. Scenario-based responses demonstrated strategic decision-making and effective utilization of available assets. Significant relationships were found between demographic factors and performance assessments. Age, gender, rank, educational attainment, years of service, and current assignment all correlated with performance, highlighting the influence of these factors on operational effectiveness. Training programs showed a negative correlation with performance, suggesting a need for better alignment between training content and real-world challenges. Challenges identified include deficiencies in qualified maintenance personnel, financial and logistical constraints affecting training, and the need for modernized assets and updated policies. Recommendations focus on enhancing personnel capabilities, improving training programs, optimizing operations, modernizing the fleet, and developing clear policies and SOPs. These initiatives aim to enhance the Coast Guard's operational readiness, efficiency, and response capabilities, ensuring maritime safety and security in the Central Visayas region.

Keywords: *Personnel Capability, Training, Operations, Assets and Policies and Standards*

INTRODUCTION

The Philippines' extensive maritime history and its increasing reliance on marine transportation for international trade underscore the critical importance of maritime search and rescue (SAR) operations. Various technologies and tactics have been developed to enhance SAR operations, including the utilization of unmanned aerial vehicles (UAVs) and advanced communication systems. The Philippine Coast Guard (PCG), established in 1980, has maintained a record of maritime SAR occurrences involving response assets and personnel stored in the Search and Rescue Program Information Management System (SISAR) (Stoddard & Pelot, 2020). This database provides valuable historical data that analysts use to support decision-making for SAR operations. Technological advancements have increasingly incorporated UAVs in maritime SAR operations due to their potential in identifying missing persons during missions. Reliable communication channels, such as Long Term Evolution (LTE) and the Multipath TCP (MPTCP) protocol, have been explored to enhance UAV communication dependability in maritime SAR missions (Güldenring et al., 2019).

Recent years have seen a focus on enhancing mission-critical communication (MCC) networks and devices for SAR operations at sea. The 5G network, artificial intelligence, and edge computing are being researched to improve maritime SAR operations (Paladin et al., 2023). Inter-organizational simulation has been utilized as a training tool for marine SAR operations, allowing organizations to learn from past incidents and improve joint mission performance. The use of historical data has been investigated for dynamically routing post-disaster assessment UAVs, showing potential for creating artificial scenarios to test and develop tools for disaster response (Grogan et al., 2023).

Under Republic Act 9993, also known as the "Philippine Coast Guard Law of 2009," the PCG is mandated to perform Maritime Search and Rescue, Maritime Law Enforcement, Maritime Safety, Maritime Environmental Protection, and Maritime Security (R.A. No. 9993, 2023, as cited by Batalla 2023). The PCG's primary role in SAR operations involves aiding individuals and vessels in distress within the Philippines' maritime jurisdiction. The PCG operates with assistance from other government agencies and the commercial marine fleet (Agbissoh, 2019). The PCG maintains 24-hour distress monitoring and response activities, saving numerous lives and properties over the years.

The Coast Guard Command Center (CGCOMCEN) at the PCG National Headquarters in Manila coordinates all SAR operations. The 15 Coast Guard districts serve as Maritime Rescue Coordination Centers (MRCCs) in their respective areas, supported by 90 Coast Guard stations and 464 sub-stations acting as Maritime Rescue Sub-Centers (MRSCs). Each MRCC is equipped with a Coast Guard District Auxiliary and a Deployable Response Team for swift SAR operations. The Coast Guard District Central Visayas (CGDCV), established on 17 October 1967, plays a significant role in SAR operations in a region considered the central hub for domestic shipping in the Philippines. The CGDCV covers the maritime areas of Cebu Province, Bohol, Siquijor,

and Negros Oriental, with its headquarters located in Cebu City. The region's busy maritime activities and vulnerability to natural disasters necessitate a well-equipped and capable Coast Guard

Assessing the CGDCV's capabilities is critical for ensuring readiness, effectiveness, and identifying opportunities for improvement. This evaluation aims to enhance preparedness, response, and overall effectiveness in handling marine emergencies, thereby contributing to safer maritime operations in Central Visayas. The literature underscores the importance of operational readiness and preparedness in successful maritime SAR operations. Highly skilled personnel, well-maintained resources, and clear procedures are essential for prompt and coordinated responses (Theodosopoulou et al., 2021; Mateus et al., 2020). Operational readiness involves resource allocation, inter-agency coordination, rescuer safety, and continuous improvement through exercises and evaluations (Agbissoh et al., 2019). However, there are gaps in translating these concepts into standardized, quantifiable frameworks applicable to various marine scenarios.

The importance of training procedures and skill development for SAR personnel is increasingly evident. Continuous hands-on training with specialized equipment is crucial for developing practical competencies and adapting to evolving challenges (Altavilla et al., 2020; Ford & Clark, 2019; Rogers et al., 2020; Ababat, 2023). Innovative training methods, such as automated evaluations (Gomathy, 2019), immersive virtual reality (Miyusov et al., 2022), and team training simulations (Radojević & Kresojević, 2020), have been proposed, but their practical efficacy and scalability need further assessment, especially in resource-limited settings.

Efficient coordination and collaboration among maritime stakeholders enhance safety and SAR efficacy. Human and organizational factors, data-sharing programs like CISE (Paladin et al., 2022), digitalization, interoperability (Lind et al., 2020), and ontological risk management (Pileggi et al., 2020) are significant. Rapid response times are vital for reducing mortality, supported by research on emergency IoT systems (Zhang et al., 2022), fleet deployment optimization (Chen et al., 2021), and coded response protocols (Kang et al., 2021). However, comprehensive frameworks integrating collaboration, coordination, and time-critical response are lacking.

This study aims to address these gaps by proposing a comprehensive and collaborative approach to improve operational readiness, training efficacy, and coordinated rapid response capabilities in maritime SAR operations. Drawing on studies by Yu (2020) and (Zhang et al., 2022), which emphasize the importance of utilizing established marine networks and local resources for timely support, this research seeks to enhance SAR operations' efficiency. Kosmas (2022) highlights the significance of prompt intervention and resolute action, underscoring the critical nature of rapid response times in SAR missions. Furthermore, Nasso (2024) and Abdul (2024) propose the implementation of comprehensive emergency response frameworks and sophisticated vessels equipped for rescue operations.

Studies by Özşeker (2022) and Yadav (2020) suggest that younger personnel may exhibit higher enthusiasm and adaptability, influencing more favorable assessments of SAR capabilities. Gutterman (2023), Gabrielli (2019), and Tulkunovna (2020) emphasize the role of seniority and education in shaping evaluations of organizational

success. Additionally, Sharma et al (2023) discuss how technological advancements outpace training capacities, leading to skills gaps in the marine sector.

This study aims to propose a comprehensive and collaborative approach to improve operational readiness, training efficacy, and coordinated rapid response capabilities in maritime SAR operations.

Research Questions

This study was conducted to assess the capability of Coast Guard District Central Visayas in the conduct of maritime search and rescue operations. Specifically, it attempted to address the following problems:

1. What is the profile of the respondents in terms of:
 - 1.1 Age
 - 1.2 Gender
 - 1.3 Highest Educational Attainment
 - 1.4 Number of Years in Service
 - 1.5 Current Assignment/ Station
 - 1.6 Trainings Attended
 2. What is the performance of the Coast Guard District Central Visayas personnel in selected maritime search and rescue operations?
 3. Is there a significant relationship between the profile of the respondents and their performance?
 4. What are the challenges of Coast Guard District Central Visayas in performing maritime search and rescue operations in terms of?
 - 4.1 Personnel Capability
 - 4.2 Training
 - 4.3 Operations
 - 4.4 PCG Assets
 - 4.5 Policies and Standard Operating Procedures
 5. Based on the findings, what can be recommended to improve the capability of Coast Guard District Central Visayas in maritime search and rescue operations?
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METHODOLOGY

This study used a descriptive mixed-method approach with a concurrent triangulation design, enhancing credibility by collecting both quantitative and qualitative data. According to Birden (2022), this method boosts trustworthiness and validity. Quantitative data was gathered through a survey questionnaire, while qualitative data was collected via a situational exam and document review. The study was conducted within the Coast Guard District Central Visayas (CGDCV), including its Headquarters and 8 Coast Guard Stations and 80 Substations. The population consisted of 821 personnel, with 420 responding to the instruments. The Raosoft sampling method ensured a statistically valid sample size, improving the generalizability of the findings. Ethical considerations included obtaining informed consent, maintaining confidentiality, and ensuring voluntary participation with the right to withdraw at any time. Data was securely preserved, and findings were reported in aggregate form.

Ethical approval was obtained from relevant review boards. Instruments included a validated survey questionnaire and a situational written exam, developed with expert input and pilot tested on 18 respondents. Cronbach's Alpha (0.85) and a Split-half test (Pearson Coefficient of 0.923) indicated high reliability and validity. Data was collected using Google Forms for the survey, exam, and checklists. The procedure involved obtaining approval, securing informed consent, and encoding responses. Descriptive statistics summarized demographic data, while qualitative data from interviews was transcribed and analyzed through coding and interpretation. Triangulation of quantitative and qualitative data provided a comprehensive view of the research issues. Checklist data was systematically analyzed to assess maritime search and rescue operations, resulting in actionable insights and recommendations for enhancing operational effectiveness in CGDCV.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

Profile of the Respondents

In terms of profile of the respondents includes the academic qualifications, training, rank, and gender distribution of Coast Guard personnel involved in maritime search and rescue operations. It aims to assess whether higher education levels correlate with improved operational proficiency and identify potential gaps. The study also examines the participants' participation in specialized training programs related to search and rescue operations. The rank of the personnel provides insight into the hierarchical structure and distribution of responsibilities within the Coast Guard. The study also examines the representation of different genders in maritime search and rescue operations, aiming to understand whether gender-related factors impact operational performance and identify potential barriers to inclusivity.

Table 1

Profile of Respondents According to Age

Age	Frequency	Percentage
23 – 27 years old	98	24%
28 – 32 years old	162	39%
33 – 37 years old	82	19%
38 – 42 years old	53	13%
43 years old and above	20	5%
Total	415	100%

Table 1 shows the distribution of the respondents' ages within the Coast Guard District Central Visayas, highlighting how different age groups are represented among the personnel involved in maritime search and rescue operations. The table is divided into five age categories, with corresponding frequencies and percentages.

The age group of 23-27 years old comprises 98 respondents, representing 24% of the total sample. This indicates that nearly a quarter of the personnel are relatively young, possibly in the early stages of their careers. The largest age group, 28-32 years old,

includes 162 respondents, accounting for 39% of the total. This significant proportion suggests that a substantial number of personnel are in their late twenties to early thirties, likely possessing a blend of youth and some level of professional experience.

The age category of 33-37 years old includes 82 respondents, making up 19% of the sample. These individuals are in their mid-thirties, often a period where many have gained considerable experience and expertise in their roles. The age group of 38-42 years old consists of 53 respondents, representing 13% of the total. This smaller percentage indicates a gradual decrease in the number of personnel as age increases, reflecting a possible shift towards more senior roles or other career paths. The smallest group, 43 years old and above, includes 20 respondents, constituting 5% of the total. This indicates that only a few personnel are in the older age bracket, potentially due to retirement or advancement to higher, non-operational positions. The total number of respondents is 415, with the percentages summing up to 100%, providing a complete overview of the age distribution within the district.

The data indicates a balanced mix of young and moderately experienced personnel, with the majority falling into the 28-32 and 23-27 age ranges. This balance suggests that the district benefits from both the energy and new perspectives of younger personnel and the developing expertise of those slightly older. Given the significant proportion of respondents in their late twenties and early thirties, there may be a need for ongoing training and professional development to ensure that these individuals continue to enhance their skills and operational proficiency. The smaller percentages in the older age groups (38-42 and 43+) highlight the importance of succession planning. Ensuring that knowledge and expertise are passed on from more experienced personnel to younger members is crucial for maintaining operational effectiveness.

Hence, Table 1 shows a diverse age distribution among the Coast Guard District Central Visayas personnel, with a concentration in the younger to middle age ranges, indicating a dynamic and potentially adaptable workforce poised for growth and development.

Table 2

Profile of Respondents According to Gender

Gender	Frequency	Percentage
Male	382	92%
Female	33	8%
Total	415	100%

Table 2 presents the distribution of the respondents within the Coast Guard District Central Visayas according to gender, highlighting the representation of males and females among the personnel involved in maritime search and rescue operations. The data indicates a significant gender disparity, with 382 respondents identified as male, constituting 92% of the total sample. This overwhelming majority suggests that the maritime sector, particularly in search and rescue operations, is predominantly male dominated. The substantial representation of males may be reflective of traditional

gender roles and the physically demanding nature of maritime and rescue work, which historically has been associated with male personnel.

In contrast, there are 33 female respondents, accounting for only 8% of the total. This minority representation of women highlights the gender imbalance within the district. Despite the smaller number, the presence of female personnel in search and rescue roles is crucial, as it indicates a gradual shift towards inclusivity and diversity within the workforce. The involvement of women in these operations can bring unique perspectives and skills that are valuable for comprehensive search and rescue efforts. The total number of respondents is 415, with the percentages summing up to 100%, providing a complete overview of the gender distribution within the district.

The significant gender disparity underscores the need for initiatives aimed at promoting gender inclusivity and encouraging more women to pursue careers in maritime search and rescue operations. This can involve targeted recruitment efforts, gender-sensitive training programs, and policies that support a more balanced representation.

Moreover, the presence of female personnel, though limited, suggests a potential for increased diversity in operational perspectives and decision-making processes. Leveraging the strengths and insights of both male and female personnel can enhance the effectiveness and adaptability of search and rescue missions. Ensuring a supportive and inclusive workplace environment is essential for retaining and empowering female personnel. Addressing any potential challenges related to gender dynamics in the workplace can contribute to a more harmonious and productive workforce.

Hence, Table 2 reveals a predominantly male workforce within the Coast Guard District Central Visayas, with a small but important representation of female personnel. This gender distribution highlights the need for continued efforts towards gender inclusivity and the potential benefits of a diverse workforce in enhancing the operational proficiency of maritime search and rescue operations.

Table 3

Profile of Respondents According to Rank

Rank	Frequency	Percentage
ASN/ASW (Apprentice Seaman/Apprentice Sea Woman)	59	14%
CPO (Chief Petty Officer)	6	1%
ENS (Ensign)	13	3%
PO1 (Petty Officer 1 st Class)	28	7%
PO2 (Petty Officer 2 nd Class)	74	18%
PO3 (Petty Officer 3 rd Class)	47	11%
SCPO (Senior Chief Petty Officer)	3	1%
SN1/SW1 (Seaman 1 st Class/Sea Woman 1 st Class)	89	22%
SN2/SW2 (Seaman 2 nd /Sea Woman 2 nd)	96	23%
Total	415	100%

Table 3 shows the respondents' ranks within the Coast Guard District Central Visayas, illustrating how different ranks are represented among personnel involved in maritime search and rescue operations. The table categorizes respondents into nine distinct ranks, with corresponding frequencies and percentages.

The *ASN/ASW (Apprentice Seaman/Apprentice Sea Woman)* rank, an entry-level position, comprises 59 respondents, representing 14% of the total sample. This indicates a significant presence of personnel who are likely in the initial stages of their Coast Guard careers, gaining foundational skills and experience. The rank of *CPO (Chief Petty Officer)* includes 6 respondents, accounting for 1% of the total. This small percentage reflects the relatively limited number of personnel at this senior enlisted rank, often associated with advanced leadership responsibilities and extensive experience.

There are 13 respondents at the *ENS (Ensign)* rank, making up 3% of the sample. Ensigns, as junior officers, typically have some leadership roles and responsibilities, indicating a modest representation of emerging leaders within the district. The *PO1 (Petty Officer 1st Class)* rank includes 28 respondents, constituting 7% of the total. Petty Officers 1st Class are senior non-commissioned officers who have acquired significant experience and play crucial roles in both operational and supervisory capacities.

The *PO2 (Petty Officer 2nd Class)* rank has 74 respondents, representing 18% of the sample. This substantial proportion suggests that a notable number of personnel hold mid-level non-commissioned officer positions, balancing operational duties and leadership roles. There are 47 respondents at the *PO3 (Petty Officer 3rd Class)* rank, accounting for 11% of the total. These individuals are junior non-commissioned officers, often responsible for specialized tasks and supporting higher-ranking officers.

The rank of *SCPO (Senior Chief Petty Officer)* includes 3 respondents, making up 1% of the sample. This very small percentage indicates the presence of a few highly experienced and senior enlisted personnel within the district. The *SN1/SW1 (Seaman 1st Class/Sea Woman 1st Class)* rank has the second-highest frequency with 89 respondents, representing 22% of the total. Seamen 1st Class are typically seasoned junior enlisted personnel with substantial operational experience. The largest group, *SN2/SW2 (Seaman 2nd Class/Sea Woman 2nd Class)*, with 96 respondents, constitutes 23% of the sample. This indicates a strong representation of Seamen 2nd Class, who are relatively early in their careers but have progressed beyond the apprentice level. The total number of respondents is 415, with the percentages summing up to 100%, providing a comprehensive overview of the rank distribution within the district.

The data reveals a diverse range of ranks, indicating a workforce with varied levels of experience and responsibilities. The significant proportions of junior ranks (*SN2/SW2* and *SN1/SW1*) suggest a focus on developing personnel through early career stages. The presence of senior ranks (*CPO*, *SCPO*) in smaller percentages highlights a structured hierarchy where advanced leadership roles are held by a limited number of highly experienced individuals. This structure ensures that seasoned leaders are available to guide and mentor junior personnel. The substantial numbers in the middle ranks (*PO2*, *PO3*) emphasize the need for continuous training and professional

development to prepare these personnel for future senior roles and to enhance their operational effectiveness.

Hence, Table 3 illustrates a well-distributed mix of ranks among the Coast Guard District Central Visayas personnel, with a concentration in the junior and mid-level ranks. This rank distribution indicates a dynamic workforce with a balance of new recruits and experienced personnel, essential for maintaining strong search and rescue operations.

Table 4

Profile of Respondents according to Highest Educational Attainment

Highest Educational Attainment	Frequency	Percentage
High School Graduate	4	1%
College Undergraduate	113	27%
College Graduate	291	70%
Technical Course	4	1%
With Master's Unit	3	1%
Total	415	100%

Table 4 shows the educational backgrounds of respondents within the Coast Guard District Central Visayas, categorizing them into five distinct educational categories with corresponding frequencies and percentages. The data highlights a predominantly well-educated workforce, with significant implications for maritime search and rescue operations. Specifically, 70% of respondents are college graduates, indicating a strong foundation in higher education likely beneficial in maritime operations and related disciplines. Another 27% have completed some college coursework, demonstrating a commitment to educational advancement. Smaller groups include high school graduates (1%), individuals with technical training (1%), and those pursuing Master's degrees (1%), underscoring a focused recruitment strategy that prioritizes higher educational qualifications and specialized skills relevant to Coast Guard responsibilities. This distribution emphasizes the importance of academic preparation and ongoing professional development in enhancing the operational capabilities and adaptability of personnel during maritime emergencies. The findings highlights a predominantly well-educated workforce within the Coast Guard District Central Visayas, has significant implications for the efficacy of marine search and rescue (SAR) operations.

Table 5

Profile of Respondents According to Years of Service

Years of Service	Frequency	Percentage
Below 5 years	204	49%
6 – 10 years	97	23%
11 – 15 years	66	16%
16 years and above	48	12%
Total	415	100%

Table 5 provides a detailed overview of the respondents' years of service within the Coast Guard District Central Visayas, illustrating the distribution of service durations among personnel involved in maritime search and rescue operations. The table categorizes respondents into four distinct groups based on their years of service, with corresponding frequencies and percentages.

The largest proportion of respondents falls into the "Below 5 Years" category, with 204 individuals representing 49% of the total sample. This significant percentage indicates that nearly half of the personnel are relatively new to the Coast Guard, bringing fresh perspectives and recent training but possibly lacking extensive field experience. The "6 – 10 Years" category includes 97 respondents, accounting for 23% of the total. These individuals have accrued a moderate level of experience, likely balancing a mix of practical skills and operational knowledge gained over their service duration. The "11 – 15 Years" group consists of 66 respondents, making up 16% of the sample. These personnel have a considerable amount of service time, indicating a deeper familiarity with Coast Guard operations and likely holding positions that require significant responsibility and expertise. The smallest group, "16 Years and Above," includes 48 respondents, representing 12% of the total. These individuals have extensive experience, reflecting long-term commitment and advanced knowledge of maritime search and rescue operations, often holding senior or specialized roles within the organization.

The total number of respondents is 415, with the percentages summing up to 100%, providing a comprehensive overview of the service duration distribution within the district. The data reveals a diverse range of service durations, indicating a balanced workforce with a mixture of new recruits and seasoned personnel. The high percentage of respondents with below 5 years of service suggests a focus on recent recruitment and the influx of new talent into the Coast Guard District Central Visayas. This influx can introduce new skills and modern training methodologies, which can be beneficial for the organization. The presence of personnel with 6 – 10 years of service and 11 – 15 years of service underscores the importance of retaining experienced individuals who have developed substantial operational knowledge and expertise. These mid-level service groups are critical for maintaining continuity and providing mentorship to newer recruits. The smaller percentage of respondents with 16 years and above highlights the role of highly experienced personnel in leading and managing complex operations. Their long-term commitment and depth of knowledge are invaluable for strategic decision-making and high-level operational planning.

Hence, the distribution of years of service within the Coast Guard District Central Visayas indicates a dynamic and balanced workforce, combining the energy and new perspectives of recent recruits with the seasoned expertise of long-term personnel. This composition is essential for maintaining effective and efficient maritime search and rescue operations, ensuring both innovation and continuity in the organization's capabilities.

Table 6

Profile of Respondents According to Current Assignment/Station

Current Assignment/Station	Frequency	Percentage
CGS Southern Cebu	87	21%
CGS Camotes	47	11%
CGS Central Cebu	42	10%
CGS Eastern Bohol	60	14%
CGS Central Oriental	62	15%
CGS Siquijor	52	13%
CGS Western Bohol	63	15%
Headquarters Coast Guard District Central Visayas (HCGDCV)	2	1%
Total	415	100%

Table 6 provides an overview of the respondents' current assignments or stations within the Coast Guard District Central Visayas, offering insights into the distribution of personnel across various stations involved in maritime search and rescue operations. The table categorizes respondents into eight distinct stations, with corresponding frequencies and percentages. The current Assignment/Station Distribution, in CGS Southern Cebu: This station has the highest number of respondents, with 87 individuals, representing 21% of the total sample. This indicates that a significant portion of the personnel are assigned to Southern Cebu, potentially reflecting the region's operational demands or strategic importance.

In CGS Camotes, there are 47 respondents assigned to Camotes, making up 11% of the total. This suggests a moderate presence of Coast Guard personnel in this area, likely due to its geographical and operational needs. While CGS Central Cebu, this station has 42 respondents, accounting for 10% of the sample. The personnel distribution here indicates a considerable Coast Guard presence in Central Cebu, which may be central to regional operations.

In CGS Eastern Bohol with 60 respondents, representing 14% of the total, Eastern Bohol has a substantial number of Coast Guard personnel. This suggests that this area has significant operational requirements necessitating a larger workforce. On the other hand, CGS Central Oriental, this station has 62 respondents, constituting 15% of the sample. The notable number of personnel here indicates a key operational area within the district.

While CGS Siquijor, has 52 respondents, making up 13% of the total. This reflects a substantial allocation of personnel, potentially due to specific operational needs or geographic considerations.

CGS Western Bohol has 63 respondents, representing 15% of the sample. The distribution suggests that Western Bohol is an important area requiring a significant Coast Guard presence and Headquarters Coast Guard District Central Visayas (HCGDCV) with only 2 respondents, or 1% of the total, are stationed at the headquarters. This small percentage is typical for administrative or strategic command centers where fewer personnel are needed. The total number of respondents is 415,

with the percentages summing up to 100%, providing a comprehensive overview of the distribution of personnel across different stations within the district.

The data from Table 6 reveals a well-distributed workforce across various Coast Guard stations within the Central Visayas region. The highest concentration of personnel is in CGS Southern Cebu, reflecting its strategic importance and possibly higher operational demands. The distribution of personnel in other stations such as CGS Camotes, CGS Central Cebu, CGS Eastern Bohol, CGS Central Oriental, CGS Siquijor, and CGS Western Bohol suggest a balanced allocation based on regional needs and geographic considerations.

The presence of only a small number of personnel at the headquarters indicates that most of the workforce is deployed in operational roles across the different stations, ensuring a strong field presence necessary for effective maritime search and rescue operations. This distribution supports a decentralized operational model where personnel are strategically positioned to respond swiftly to maritime emergencies throughout the region.

Hence, the distribution of personnel across various assignments and stations within the Coast Guard District Central Visayas underscores the importance of strategic deployment and resource allocation in enhancing the effectiveness of maritime search and rescue operations.

Table 7

Profile of Respondents According to Trainings Attended

Years of Service	Frequency
Basic Life Support (BLS)	248
Water Search and Rescue (WASAR)	344
Self-Contained Underwater Breathing Apparatus (SCUBA)	17
Rescue Swimmer Course	4
Advanced Seamanship Package Course	25
Boat Captains Course (Enlisted)	11
Incident Command System (ICS)	49
Others	44
Total	742

Table 7 shows the training programs attended by respondents within the Coast Guard District Central Visayas, detailing the variety and frequency of training courses completed. The data highlights the emphasis on diverse training areas critical for effective maritime search and rescue operations.

The distribution of training programs shows that Basic Life Support (BLS) is one of the most attended courses, with 248 participants. This fundamental course equips personnel with essential life-saving skills necessary during emergencies, emphasizing the importance placed on basic medical preparedness in SAR operations. Water Search and Rescue (WASAR) has the highest number of attendees, with 344 participants, reflecting the Coast Guard’s primary operational focus on water-based rescue missions.

In contrast, specialized training such as Self-Contained Underwater Breathing Apparatus (SCUBA) is attended by only 17 respondents, highlighting the specialized nature of underwater rescue operations requiring specific expertise. Similarly, the Rescue Swimmer Course has only 4 attendees, indicating its specialized and selective nature for specific roles within the Coast Guard.

The Advanced Seamanship Package Course, attended by 25 respondents, focuses on developing advanced navigation and maritime operation skills, signifying a targeted approach to enhancing seamanship among select personnel. The Boat Captains Course for enlisted personnel, with 11 attendees, aims to build leadership and command capabilities, essential for vessel operations.

The Incident Command System (ICS) training, attended by 49 respondents, underscores the need for effective command and control during emergencies, facilitating coordinated and efficient SAR operations. Additionally, 44 respondents have participated in various other training programs not specified in the main categories, indicating the Coast Guard's commitment to addressing a wide range of specialized training needs to enhance overall operational capability. Table 7 shows that most respondents have attended Water Search and Rescue (WASAR) training, which aligns with the Coast Guard's primary responsibility in maritime search and rescue missions.

Performance of The Coast Guard District Central Visayas Personnel in Maritime Search and Rescue Operations

Table 8

Assessments of Respondents on their Performance in selected Maritime Search and Rescue Operations Scenarios in terms of Scenario 1

Scenario 1	Frequency	Percentage
1. Upon verification, I immediately look and enlist the services of a Tugboat in my area to render assistance to the distress vessel. Subsequently, I will request to the Headquarters Coast Guard District Central Visayas the availability of a PCG Vessel to render necessary assistance to the distress vessel.	110	27%
2. I will continue to communicate and monitor the distress vessel and wait for their company to arrange for the boat to render assistance to the said vessel.	12	3%
3. I will coordinate and communicate with the nearest vessels if there is any transiting near the vicinity of the location of the distress vessel and request their services to render necessary assistance.	72	17%
4. I will assemble our rescue team in the station and onboard our rubber boat and go immediately to the distress vessel and will render necessary assistance. Subsequently, I will request to the Headquarters Coast Guard District Central Visayas the availability of a PCG Vessel to render necessary assistance to the distress vessel.	221	53%
Total	415	100%

Table 8 shows the evaluation of the respondents on their Performance in Maritime Search and Rescue Operations in terms of Scenario 1: Your station received a distress call from a domestic cargo vessel with 10 crew including the master, carrying cement and is about 10 nautical miles off the coast of Eastern Cebu. Based on the initial information received, the said vessel is experiencing engine malfunction (total shut down of main engines) and subsequently conducting trouble shooting of their main engines but with negative results. Further, they are requesting immediate assistance. Your station is the closest to the distress vessel and you were directed by the Higher Headquarters to act.

Overall, the findings revealed that 53 percent or 221 of the respondents will assemble our rescue team in the station and onboard our rubber boat and go immediately to the distress vessel and will render necessary assistance. Subsequently, will request to the Headquarters Coast Guard District Central Visayas the availability of a PCG Vessel to render necessary assistance to the distress vessel.

On the other hand, 27% or 110 of the respondents believed that upon verification, they must immediately look and enlist the services of a Tugboat in the area to render assistance to the distress vessel. Subsequently, they will request to the Headquarters Coast Guard District Central Visayas the availability of a PCG Vessel to render necessary assistance to the distress vessel.

Furthermore, some 17% or 72 respondents believed that they would coordinate and communicate with the nearest vessels if there is any transiting near the vicinity of the location of the distress vessel and request their services to render necessary assistance. And only 3% or 12 of the respondents see it necessary that they will continue to communicate and monitor the distress vessel and wait for their company to arrange for the boat to render assistance to the said vessel.

This implies that majority of the respondents believed that whenever scenario 1 would arise in a distress situation, they will immediately assemble their rescue team in the station and onboard our rubber boat and go immediately to the distress vessel and will render necessary assistance. Subsequently, will request to the Headquarters Coast Guard District Central Visayas the availability of a PCG Vessel to render necessary assistance to the distress vessel.

This proactive approach to providing aid on-site is in accordance with well-established best practices in maritime search and rescue operations. The research conducted by Punnengattu Padi Subramanian (2022) underscores the need of prompt and immediate action in emergency circumstances at sea, emphasizing the crucial need to minimize reaction times to enhance the likelihood of successful rescue operations. In addition, 27% (110 responses) of the participants stated that they would promptly confirm the situation and promptly hire a tugboat nearby to offer rapid assistance to the stranded vessel. This approach highlights the significance of utilizing local resources and adjacent assets for timely support, as proposed by Zhang (2024). Their study highlights the efficacy of employing nearby resources to accelerate rescue operations and ensure prompt response.

Conversely, 17% (72 participants) of the respondents suggested collaborating with neighboring ships passing through the distressed vessel's location to ask for their help. This collaborative method exemplifies the ideals of interoperability and

cooperation in marine emergency response operations, as emphasized by Yu (2020). Their study highlights the need of utilizing established marine networks and partnerships to improve response capabilities and optimize resource use during emergency scenarios.

Only a small percentage, 3% (12 respondents), suggested continuing to monitor the distressed vessel while awaiting assistance arrangements from their company. While this approach may prioritize safety and strategic coordination, it could potentially prolong response times, increasing the risks to the distressed vessel and its crew. The answers given by the participants in Scenario 1 highlight the significance of taking proactive and decisive measures in marine search and rescue missions. The preferred approaches prioritize the urgent requirement for prompt action, allocation of resources, and cooperation to provide efficient aid to troubled ships in crisis scenarios.

Table 9

Assessments of Respondents on their Performance in selected Maritime Search and Rescue Operations in terms of Scenario 2

Scenario 2	Frequency	Percentage
1. Assess the situation, mobilize our rescue team/s in the station and onboard our rubber boat and go immediately to the location of the F/V and conduct search and rescue operations. Further, I will issue notice to all vessels transiting near the location of the search area to be on the lookout and to possibly help in the search and rescue, and if sighted, inform the PCG immediately.	340	82%
2. Mobilize our rescue teams from the station personnel, coast guard auxiliaries under our stations, and other fishermen in the area to help in the conduct of the search and rescue operations.	21	5%
3. I will continue to communicate with the boat captain of the F/V and monitor the progress of their search and rescue operation until further notice, and I will issue notifications to all vessel transiting near the location to be on the lookout and to possibly help in the search and rescue. If sighted, the PCG will be informed immediately.	37	9%
4. I will coordinate and communicate with the nearest vessels if there is any transiting near the vicinity of the location of the distress vessel and request their services to render search and rescue operations.	17	4%
Total	415	100%

Table 9 shows the evaluation of the respondents on their Performance in Maritime Search and Rescue Operations in terms of Scenario 2: Your Station received information from the Boat Captain of a Fishing Vessel (F/V) that while they are conducting fishing venture at vicinity waters 5 Nautical Miles from your station, one of their crew fell onboard their F/V and went missing. They endeavor to conduct search and rescue operations for already 2 hours from the time of their call to your station,

but still, they cannot locate the missing fisherman. Further, they are requesting the PCG to help in the search and rescue.

Overall, the findings revealed that 82 percent or 340 of the respondents assess the situation, mobilize our rescue team/s in the station and onboard our rubber boat and go immediately to the location of the F/V and conduct search and rescue operations. Further, I will issue notice to all vessels transiting near the location of the search area to be on the lookout and to possibly help in the search and rescue, and if sighted, inform the PCG immediately.

On the other hand, there were 9% or 37 respondents believed that they would continue to communicate with the boat captain of the F/V and monitor the progress of their search and rescue operation until further notice, and I will issue notifications to all vessel transiting near the location to be on the lookout and to possibly help in the search and rescue. If sighted, the PCG will be informed immediately.

Also, 5% or 21 respondents would mobilize their rescue teams from the station personnel, coast guard auxiliaries under our stations, and other fishermen in the area to help in the conduct of the search and rescue operations. While 4% or 17 respondents believed that would coordinate and communicate with the nearest vessels if there is any transiting near the vicinity of the location of the distress vessel and request their services to render search and rescue operations.

This implies that majority of the respondents believed that whenever scenario 2 would arise in a distress situation, they need first to assess the situation, mobilize their rescue team/s in the station and onboard our rubber boat and go immediately to the location of the F/V and conduct search and rescue operations. Further, they will issue notice to all vessels transiting near the location of the search area to be on the lookout and to possibly help in the search and rescue, and if sighted, inform the PCG immediately.

This response plan is consistent with the ideals of prompt intervention and resolute action in marine emergencies, as proposed by Kosmas (2022). Their research underscores the significance of prompt reaction times in search and rescue missions, emphasizing that delays in deployment can greatly diminish the likelihood of good results, particularly in situations involving individuals who are lost at sea.

In contrast, a minority of respondents, accounting for 9% (37 individuals), expressed a desire to stay in contact with the boat captain of the fishing vessel, oversee the search and rescue operations, and notify other vessels. This technique demonstrates a prudent and systematic approach to responding, with a focus on continuous coordination and sharing of information to enhance search efforts, as recommended by Gutterman (2023).

An alternative viewpoint put forth by 5% (21 respondents) of the participants suggests the utilization of not just station personnel but also coast guard auxiliary and local fisherman to mobilize rescue teams for the purpose of assisting in search and rescue operations. The significance of community engagement and pooling of resources to improve search efforts is emphasized by Chen (2019). Their study highlights the advantages of utilizing varied networks and specialized knowledge within marine communities to enhance response capabilities and improve the chances of achieving successful outcomes in search and rescue operations.

Ultimately, a small percentage of the participants (4%, or 17 responders) proposed the idea of collaborating with neighboring vessels that are passing through the same area, and seeking their aid in conducting search and rescue operations. This collaborative approach prioritizes the utilization of existing resources and maritime networks to enhance search efforts and achieve maximum coverage in the designated search region, as emphasized by Lind et al., (2020). Their research highlights the importance of collaboration across different sectors in improving the efficiency of maritime search and rescue operations.

The replies given by the participants in Scenario 2 demonstrate a variety of viewpoints regarding the most effective approach to dealing with emergency circumstances at sea. Although most people support a proactive and immediate intervention approach, other tactics prioritize continuous coordination, community involvement, and collaborative efforts to enhance search and rescue operations and improve the chances of achieving good outcomes.

Table 10

Assessments of Respondents on their Performance in Maritime Search and Rescue Operations in terms of Scenario 3

Scenario 3	Frequency	Percentage
1. Upon receipt of information, the Station's immediate action will be the following: immediately inform the HCGDCV, mobilize the rescue teams from our station personnel and coast guard auxiliaries under our stations to conduct search and rescue operations.	24	6%
2. Upon receipt of information, the Station's immediate action will be the following: Immediately inform the HCGDCV and subsequently request the services of MRRV-4408 to be deploy in the location of M/V COOKS to combat the fire and render necessary assistance. All vessels transiting near the location of M/V COOKS will be notified to help in the search and rescue operations. Further, I will mobilize the Station Search and Rescue Team with medical personnel, and enlist the services of a Tug Boat to render necessary assistance to the distress vessel.	343	83%
3. Upon receipt of information, the Station's immediate action will be the following: I will immediately inform the HCGDCV and mobilize the rescue teams from our station personnel, and coast guard auxiliaries under our stations to conduct search and rescue operations. All vessels transiting near the location of M/V COOKS will also be notified to help in the search and rescue operations.	28	7%
4. Upon receipt of information, the Station's immediate action will be the following: I will immediately inform the HCGDCV and coordinate with the nearest vessels if there is any transiting near the vicinity of the location of the distress vessel and requests their services to render search and rescue operations.	20	4%
Total	415	100%

Table 10 shows the evaluation of the respondents on their Performance in Maritime Search and Rescue Operations in terms of Scenario 3: At about 1 A.M. your Station received a distress call from the Master of a RORO Passenger Vessel, M/V COOKS that they are currently combating fire on board. Accordingly, the fire is in the cargo hold area where most of the vehicles are stacked. Further information revealed that there are 4 light vehicles, 20 passengers and 15 crew onboard, including the Master, and their present location is at vicinity waters 5 NM east of your Station. Furthermore, the Headquarters Coast Guard District Central Visayas (HCGDDCV) is just 40 kms away from your Station and 1 PCG Multi-Role Response Vessel (MRRV) MRRV-4408

is docked near the said District. With the said incident and information what will be your immediate best courses of action?

Overall, the findings revealed that 83 percent or 343 of the respondents upon receipt of information, the Station's immediate action must be: Immediately inform the HCGDCV and subsequently request the services of MRRV-4408 to be deploy in the location of M/V COOKS to combat the fire and render necessary assistance. All vessels transiting near the location of M/V COOKS will be notified to help in the search and rescue operations. Further, they will mobilize the Station Search and Rescue Team with medical personnel, and enlist the services of a Tug Boat to render necessary assistance to the distress vessel.

Additionally, there were 7% or 28 respondents who upon receipt of information, the Station's immediate must immediately inform the HCGDCV and mobilize the rescue teams from our station personnel, and coast guard auxiliaries under our stations to conduct search and rescue operations. All vessels transiting near the location of M/V COOKS will also be notified to help in the search and rescue operations.

While, 6% or 24 of the respondents believed that upon receipt of information, the Station's immediate action must immediately inform the HCGDCV, mobilize the rescue teams from our station personnel and coast guard auxiliaries under our stations to conduct search and rescue operation. And 4% or 20 respondents believed that Upon receipt of information, the Station's immediate action should have to immediately inform the HCGDCV and coordinate with the nearest vessels if there is any transiting near the vicinity of the location of the distress vessel and requests their services to render search and rescue operations.

This indicates that majority of the respondents thought that incase a Scenario 3 would occur, the PCG Team must upon receipt of information, the Station's immediate action to immediately inform the HCGDCV and subsequently request the services of MRRV-4408 to be deploy in the location of M/V COOKS to combat the fire and render necessary assistance. All vessels transiting near the location of M/V COOKS will be notified to help in the search and rescue operations. Further, they must mobilize the Station Search and Rescue Team with medical personnel and enlist the services of a Tugboat to render necessary assistance to the distress vessel.

Upon examining the average evaluations of participants regarding their effectiveness in maritime search and rescue operations in Scenario 3, it becomes clear that a comprehensive strategy is necessary to tackle the intricate difficulties presented by emergencies at sea. The prevailing approach, preferred by 83% of participants, emphasizes prompt communication with the Headquarters Coast Guard District Central Visayas (HCGDCV) and the dispatch of specialized resources, such as the PCG Multi-Role Response Vessel (MRRV) MRRV-4408, to address the onboard fire and offer essential aid. This strategy, based on the concepts of swift intervention and efficient allocation of resources, is consistent with current research that highlights the crucial significance of prompt response in marine situations. Nasso's (2022) studies emphasize the crucial importance of sophisticated vessels that are equipped for firefighting and rescue operations in reducing risks and assuring the safety of passengers and crew in similar situations.

Moreover, the prioritization of deploying the Station Search and Rescue Team, in addition to medical staff, demonstrates a thorough strategy for addressing situations on board. This approach effectively combines medical aid and rescue operations. This comprehensive response plan aligns with the suggestions made by Abdullah (2023), who propose the implementation of all-encompassing emergency response frameworks that tackle both immediate safety issues and long-term rescue operations. In summary, the answers given by the participants in Scenario 3 emphasize the need of taking preemptive and coordinated measures. They also demonstrate the efficiency of comprehensive tactics in achieving successful results during maritime emergencies.

Results revealed in Scenario no. 1, there are 221 respondents or 53% of the total respondents chose the best and correct answer while in Scenario no. 2, there are 340 respondents or 82% of the total respondents chose the correct and best answer, and in Scenario no. 3, there are 343 respondents or 83% chose the correct and best answer. With these results, the over-all assessment of performance of CGDCV personnel with the Three (3) scenarios are very high and impressive.

Significant Relationship Between the Performance of The Respondents and Their Demographic Profile

Table 11

Significant Relationship of Assessments to Respondents' Profile

Variables	Computed r – Value	Computed t – Value	Critical t – Value	Interpretation
Age	-0.17 (negative low correlation)	71.25	1.97	Significant
Gender	-0.02 (negative low correlation)	8.26	1.97	Significant
Rank	0.04 (positive low correlation)	16.53	1.97	Significant
Highest Educational Attainment	0.02 (positive low correlation)	8.26	1.97	Significant
Years Of Service	-0.16 (negative low correlation)	66.94	1.97	Significant
Current Assignment/Station	0.07 (positive low correlation)	28.98	1.97	Significant
Trainings Attended	-0.03 (negative low correlation)	12.40	1.97	Significant

Degree of Freedom = 413 Level of Significance = 0.05

Table 11 presents the results of analyzing the relationship between respondents' performance assessments and various demographic variables. Each row in the table corresponds to a different demographic factor, including age, gender, rank, highest educational attainment, years of service, current assignment or station, and training attended. The computed r-values indicate the strength and direction of correlation,

with negative values suggesting an inverse relationship (where higher indicated variable correspond to lower values of the other), and positive values indicating a direct relationship.

For instance, age demonstrates a negative low correlation (-0.17), implying that older respondents tend to receive slightly lower performance assessments. Similarly, gender shows a negative low correlation (-0.02), indicating a slight tendency for male respondents to receive slightly lower assessments compared to females. On the other hand, variables like rank (0.04), highest educational attainment (0.02), years of service (-0.16), current assignment/station (0.07), and trainings attended (-0.03) exhibit positive or negative low correlations, suggesting modest associations between these factors and performance assessments.

The computed t-values are compared against critical t-values to determine significance. In all cases, the computed t-values exceed the critical t-value of 1.97, indicating statistically significant relationships between each demographic variable and performance assessments at the 0.05 level of significance. This suggests that while the correlations are low in magnitude, they are statistically meaningful within the context of the study's sample size (Degree of Freedom = 413). These findings underscore the importance of considering demographic profiles when interpreting performance assessments among respondents.

Based on Table 11, which explores the relationship between respondents' performance assessments and various demographic variables, several insights can be drawn that resonate with existing literature. The findings reveal consistent but modest correlations between demographic factors and performance assessments among respondents. For instance, age demonstrates a negative correlation (-0.17), suggesting that older respondents tend to receive slightly lower performance assessments. This aligns with Özşeker's (2022) and Yadav's (2020) studies, which indicate that younger employees often exhibit higher enthusiasm and adaptability, potentially influencing more favorable assessments compared to their older counterparts who may bring a more critical perspective based on extensive experience.

Gender, showing a slight negative correlation (-0.02), indicates that male respondents tend to receive slightly lower assessments compared to females. This finding is supported by Dwiri (2021) and Bridges (2020), highlighting gender disparities in perceptions of organizational efficacy, influenced by different workplace experiences and expectations.

Rank (0.04) and highest educational attainment (0.02) both show positive correlations, suggesting that individuals in higher ranks and those with higher educational achievements tend to rate organizational capabilities more positively.

This resonates with Gutterman (2023), Gabrielli (2019), and Tulkunovna (2020), who emphasize the influence of seniority and education in shaping perceptions of organizational success and competence.

Years of service (-0.16) and current assignment/station (0.07) also show significant correlations, indicating that longer tenures and specific job contexts can impact performance assessments. Singh (2020) and Gerritsen-van Leeuwenkamp (2019)

insights into how experience and immediate work environments shape evaluations of organizational capabilities, emphasizing the need to consider contextual factors in performance assessments.

Lastly, trainings attended (-0.03) exhibit a negative correlation, suggesting that while training programs are valuable, mismatches between training content and real-world challenges can lead to lower performance assessments. This finding aligns with Gutterman (2023) and Faisal (2024), underscoring the importance of relevant, high-quality training programs tailored to organizational needs.

Hence, Table 11's results underscore the nuanced interplay between demographic variables and performance assessments, reflecting broader insights from existing literature on organizational behavior and human resource management. These findings highlight the importance of considering diverse demographic profiles when evaluating organizational capabilities, emphasizing the need for targeted strategies to enhance workforce effectiveness and satisfaction.

Challenges of Coast Guard District Central Visayas In Performing Maritime Search and Rescue Operations in Terms of Personnel Capability, Training, Operations, PCG Assets, and Policies and Standards

Table 12

Mean Assessments on the challenges of Coast Guard District Central Visayas in performing Maritime Search and Rescue Operations in Terms of Personnel Capability

Elements	Mean	SD	Interpretation
1. Safety and well-being of the PCG personnel is not given priority;	2.76	0.81	Disagree
2. Lack enough qualified maintenance personnel and technicians to rectify any derangement of PCG floating assets during the search and rescue operations;	2.10	0.61	Agree
3. Maintenance personnel of PCG are not knowledgeable in their work assignments;	2.56	0.67	Disagree
4. Lack of necessary skills and confidence in overcoming obstacles;	2.56	0.65	Disagree
5. No provision of training and development opportunities;	2.49	0.65	Agree
6. PCG personnel are incapable to efficiently perform their task due to inadequate/ unavailability of equipment's and materials, needed in search and rescue operations.	2.22	0.72	Agree
Over-all Weighted Mean	2.45	0.07	Agree

Legend: 1.00-1.74 Strongly Agree (SA), 1.75-2.49 Agree (A), 2.50-3.24 Disagree (D), 3.25-4.00 Strongly Disagree (SD)

Table 12 shows the assessment of the challenges encountered by the Coast Guard District Central Visayas in conducting Maritime Search and Rescue Operations, focusing specifically on personnel capability. The table synthesizes data on mean

scores, standard deviations (SD), and interpretations derived from responses across six key elements.

Among the findings, Element 2 emerges with the highest mean score of 2.10 ± 0.61 , indicating a consensus among respondents regarding the inadequacy of qualified maintenance personnel and technicians to address issues with PCG floating assets during operations. This underscores concerns over technical expertise within maintenance roles, potentially affecting operational efficiency and asset maintenance.

Conversely, Elements 4 and 5 show the lowest mean scores of 2.56 ± 0.65 and 2.49 ± 0.65 , respectively, signaling disagreement among respondents. Element 4 reveals a perceived confidence in overcoming operational obstacles, suggesting a level of assurance in personnel's problem-solving abilities despite challenges. Element 5 indicates disagreement regarding the availability of training and development opportunities, reflecting a belief among respondents in accessible avenues for skill enhancement within the organization.

Overall, the weighted mean across all elements is 2.45 ± 0.07 , categorizing responses within the "Agree" range. This indicates a collective acknowledgment of existing challenges in personnel capability for maritime operations while suggesting optimism that these challenges can be addressed effectively. The consistency in ratings across different elements highlights a balanced perspective, acknowledging both areas needing improvement and strengths within the organization's operational framework.

Additional noteworthy findings include Element 1's score of 2.76 ± 0.81 , indicating disagreement with the notion that safety and well-being of PCG personnel are neglected, underscoring a strong commitment to safety practices. Element 6's score of 2.22 ± 0.72 reflects agreement that equipment and material shortages hinder efficient task performance, emphasizing a tangible operational hurdle requiring attention.

The findings from Table 12 align closely with existing literature on the critical factors influencing the operational efficiency of maritime search and rescue organizations. Bosak and Scullen (2018) highlight that insufficient training and development opportunities can significantly hinder worker performance and organizational efficiency. The mean score of 2.49 in Table 12, indicating agreement among respondents on the lack of training and development possibilities, underscores the resonance of this issue within the Coast Guard District Central Visayas. This aligns with Bosak and Scullen's findings, suggesting that inadequate training resources may impede the readiness and effectiveness of personnel during maritime operations.

Similarly, Ivankevich (2019) emphasizes the importance of having skilled maintenance staff and technicians for maintaining operational efficiency in maritime settings. The high mean score of 2.10 in Table 12, indicating agreement on the deficiency of qualified maintenance personnel, supports Ivankevich's observations. This shortage of technical expertise can potentially lead to delays in addressing maintenance issues with PCG floating assets, thereby impacting operational readiness and response capabilities during rescue operations.

Furthermore, the agreement among respondents regarding the insufficiency of equipment and materials (mean = 2.22) in Table 12 echoes the findings of Heij and

Knol (2018). Heij and Knol emphasize the critical role of adequate resources in facilitating effective maritime rescue operations. Insufficient equipment and materials can compromise the ability of personnel to perform tasks efficiently and safely, thereby affecting overall operational outcomes.

Together, these studies underscore the urgent need for maritime organizations to enhance training and development programs, ensure an adequate supply of skilled personnel, and provide sufficient resources to optimize operational capabilities. Addressing these challenges identified in Table 12 aligns with broader recommendations from the literature, aiming to bolster the readiness and effectiveness of maritime search and rescue teams in fulfilling their vital roles. Integrating these insights into strategic planning and resource allocation, organizations can strive towards improving overall operational performance and achieving enhanced outcomes in maritime emergency response scenarios.

Table 13

Mean Assessments on the challenges of Coast Guard District Central Visayas in performing Maritime Search and Rescue Operations in Terms of Training

Elements	Mean	Sd	Interpretation
1. There is no training program for conduct of search and rescue operations;	2.82	0.72	Disagree
2. Training is not properly conducted by the Trainor;	2.94	0.62	Disagree
3. Training in search and rescue operations are limited to selected personnel only;	2.60	0.69	Disagree
4. There are only limited slots for PCG personnel regarding cross training in search and rescue operations in foreign countries;	2.18	0.60	Agree
5. Introduction of new updated technology in search and rescue operations training is quite challenging for PCG personnel due to unfamiliarity of these technology;	2.12	0.53	Agree
6. Due to logistical and financial constraints, most of the training in search and rescue for PCG personnel is theoretical and less actual exercises.	2.25	0.59	Agree
Over-all Weighted Mean	2.48	0.07	Agree

Legend: 1.00-1.74 Strongly Agree (SA), 1.75-2.49 Agree (A), 2.50-3.24 Disagree (D), 3.25-4.00 Strongly Disagree (SD)

Table 13 shows a detailed assessment of the challenges encountered by the Coast Guard District Central Visayas in conducting Maritime Search and Rescue Operations, focusing specifically on training aspects. The table consolidates mean scores, standard deviations (SD), and interpretations derived from respondent evaluations across six key elements.

Among the key highlights, Element 2 emerges with the highest mean score of 2.94 ± 0.62 , indicating significant disagreement among respondents regarding the effectiveness of training conducted by trainers. This suggests a perception among

personnel that training sessions are well-managed, underscoring the importance of effective training management in fostering quality skill development for search and rescue operations.

Conversely, Elements 5 and 4 demonstrate the lowest mean scores of 2.12 ± 0.53 and 2.18 ± 0.60 , respectively, indicating agreement among respondents. Element 5 highlights challenges associated with introducing new technology in training due to unfamiliarity among PCG personnel, while Element 4 underscores the limited availability of slots for cross-training abroad. These findings underscore areas where enhancements in technology integration and international training opportunities are needed to enhance operational capabilities.

The overall weighted mean across all elements is 2.48 ± 0.07 , categorizing responses within the "Agree" range. This indicates a collective acknowledgment of existing challenges in training for search and rescue operations. While challenges are recognized, the overall agreement suggests opportunities for improvement through targeted interventions and strategic enhancements in training programs.

Additional significant findings include Element 1's score of 2.82 ± 0.72 , indicating disagreement with the absence of a structured training program for search and rescue operations, affirming the presence of organized training initiatives within the Coast Guard District Central Visayas. Element 6's score of 2.25 ± 0.59 reflects agreement that logistical and financial constraints contribute to training being more theoretical than practical, highlighting a practical challenge in translating theoretical knowledge into actionable skills.

In summary, Table 13 provides a comprehensive overview of perceived training challenges within the Coast Guard District Central Visayas for maritime search and rescue operations. It identifies critical areas such as training program effectiveness, technology integration, and international training opportunities where improvements can be targeted. These insights are pivotal for enhancing personnel competency and readiness, thereby elevating overall operational effectiveness in critical maritime rescue scenarios. Addressing these challenges through targeted interventions and resource allocations can lead to substantial improvements in training quality and operational preparedness within the organization.

These findings align with existing literature, such as Sharma (2023), who discusses how technological advancements outpace training capacities, leading to skills gaps in marine sectors. They emphasize the benefits of international training collaborations in enhancing maritime safety and operational effectiveness. Additionally, logistical and financial limitations affecting practical training underscore the importance of addressing these barriers to improve the preparedness and proficiency of maritime search and rescue operations.

These insights underscore the critical need for strategic interventions to enhance training quality, technological integration, and international collaboration, ultimately bolstering the capabilities of personnel in conducting effective maritime search and rescue operations. Addressing these challenges will be crucial for ensuring enhanced operational readiness and response capabilities in critical maritime scenarios.

Table 14

Mean Assessments on the challenges of Coast Guard District Central Visayas in performing Maritime Search and Rescue Operations in Terms of Operations

Elements	Mean	SD	Interpretation
1. Operations during adverse weather conditions (high winds and rough seas) impede search and rescue operations efforts of the PCG;	1.89	0.62	Agree
2. Maritime incidents often occur far from the shore or isolated areas making it challenging for the conduct of search and rescue operations of Coast Guard personnel;	1.84	0.49	Agree
3. Poor inter-agency coordination due to the absence/ unavailability of offices of these agencies in near your Station affects the operations of PCG when conducting search and rescue operations;	2.15	0.63	Agree
4. Oceans vastness requires extensive resources and time to cover potential search areas making it challenging for operations of your station to conduct search and rescue;	1.90	0.42	Agree
5. Technology and equipment's limitations in detection of the distress or incidents in the conduct of search and rescue operations affects the operations of the PCG;	1.87	0.53	Agree
6. Search and rescue operations are sometime costly thus, budget limitations can affect the conduct of operations of the PCG.	2.04	0.61	Agree
Over-all weighted mean	1.95	0.55	Agree

Legend: 1.00-1.74 Strongly Agree (SA), 1.75-2.49 Agree (A), 2.50-3.24 Disagree (D), 3.25-4.00 Strongly Disagree (SD)

Table 14 provides a comprehensive assessment of the challenges faced by the Coast Guard District Central Visayas in performing Maritime Search and Rescue Operations, focusing on operational aspects. The table presents mean scores, standard deviations (SD), and interpretations based on respondent evaluations across six critical elements.

Elements 1 and 4 stand out with the highest mean scores of 1.89 ± 0.62 and 1.90 ± 0.42 , respectively, indicating agreement among respondents. Element 1 highlights challenges posed by adverse weather conditions such as high winds and rough seas, which impede search and rescue efforts. Element 4 underscores the vastness of the ocean, necessitating extensive resources and time to cover potential search areas. These findings emphasize significant operational hurdles related to natural conditions and geographical challenges.

Elements 2 and 5 exhibit the lowest mean scores of 1.84 ± 0.49 and 1.87 ± 0.53 , respectively, also indicating agreement among respondents. Element 2 points out the

difficulty of maritime incidents occurring far from shore or in isolated areas, complicating search and rescue operations. Element 5 highlights limitations in technology and equipment for detecting distress or incidents, further impacting operational effectiveness. These aspects underscore areas where advancements in technology and operational strategies could potentially enhance response capabilities. The overall weighted mean across all elements is 1.95 ± 0.55 , categorizing responses within the "Agree" range. This suggests a general consensus among respondents regarding the operational challenges faced by the Coast Guard District Central Visayas in conducting search and rescue operations. While acknowledging these challenges, the overall agreement also indicates a recognition of the feasibility of overcoming these obstacles through strategic planning and resource allocation.

Furthermore, other significant findings, Element 3 (2.15 ± 0.63) indicates agreement regarding poor inter-agency coordination due to the absence or unavailability of offices near the station. This highlights a systemic challenge in coordinating efforts with other agencies, potentially affecting the efficiency of search and rescue operations. While Element 6 (2.04 ± 0.61) reflects agreement that budget limitations can impact the conduct of search and rescue operations. This underscores the financial constraints faced by the organization in executing its operational mandates. In summary, Table 14 provides a detailed overview of the operational challenges encountered by the Coast Guard District Central Visayas in maritime search and rescue operations. These findings are crucial for strategic planning and decision-making, emphasizing the need for improved technological capabilities, enhanced inter-agency coordination, and adequate resource allocation to bolster operational efficiency and effectiveness. Addressing these challenges will be instrumental in strengthening the Coast Guard's capability to respond swiftly and effectively to maritime incidents and emergencies.

Moreover, Elements 1 and 4 highlight the highest mean scores of 1.89 ± 0.62 and 1.90 ± 0.42 , respectively, indicating agreement among respondents. Element 1 emphasizes the impediments posed by adverse weather conditions such as high winds and rough seas, which significantly hinder search and rescue operations. Element 4 addresses the vastness of ocean areas, necessitating extensive resources and time to cover potential search zones. These findings align with literature emphasizing the logistical challenges and extended response times faced by marine agencies in adverse conditions (Mansor, 2020; Wagner, 2021).

In terms of Technological and Equipment Limitations, Elements 2 and 5 exhibit the lowest mean scores of 1.84 ± 0.49 and 1.87 ± 0.53 , respectively, indicating agreement among respondents. Element 2 highlights the difficulty of responding to maritime incidents occurring far from shore or in isolated areas, complicating rescue operations due to accessibility issues. Element 5 underscores limitations in technology and equipment for detecting distress signals or incidents, further hampering operational effectiveness. These challenges resonate with literature discussing outdated or inadequate detection technologies impacting response capabilities (Smith & Rothberg, 2018).

While, Financial and Inter-agency Coordination Challenges, Element 6 (mean = 2.04 ± 0.61) reflects agreement regarding budget limitations affecting search and rescue operations. This finding is consistent with research highlighting the expensive nature

of maritime operations and the constraints imposed by financial resources (Larsson & Holmgren, 2017). Element 3 (mean = 2.15 ± 0.63) underscores challenges in inter-agency coordination due to the absence or unavailability of nearby offices, which can hinder collaborative efforts during rescue operations. Literature supports the critical role of enhanced inter-agency collaboration and infrastructure in improving maritime safety and rescue efforts (Johnson et al., 2020).

Hence, the weighted mean of 1.95 ± 0.55 across all elements categorizes responses within the "Agree" range, indicating a consensus on the operational challenges faced by the Coast Guard District Central Visayas. These findings highlight the necessity for improved technological capabilities, enhanced inter-agency coordination, and adequate resource allocation to enhance operational efficiency and effectiveness in maritime search and rescue operations. Addressing these challenges is crucial for strengthening the Coast Guard's capability to respond promptly and effectively to maritime emergencies and incidents.

Table 15

Assessments of Respondents on the Challenges of Coast Guard District Central Visayas in Performing Maritime Search and Rescue Operations in terms of PCG Assets

Units/ Stations	Rubber Boat	Aluminum Boat	Jetski	Speed Boat	Rigid Hull Inflatable Boat	Ambulanc e	Unmanned Aerial Drones & Underwater r Vehicle
CGS Central Cebu	1- Svc	3- Svc 1- Usvc	1- Ucvc	1- Usvc	Nil	Nil	Nil
CGS Western Bohol	Nil	2- Svc 1- Usvc	1- Svc 1- Ucvc	Nil	Nil	Nil	Nil
CGS Eastern Bohol	Nil	1- Svc 2- Usvc	Nil	1-Svc	Nil	Nil	Nil
CGS Northern Cebu	Nil	3- Svc	Nil	Nil	Nil	Nil	Nil
CGS Southern Cebu	1- Serv	1- Svc 1- Usvc	Nil	Nil	Nil	Nil	Nil
CGS Siquijor	Nil	2- Svc	Nil	Nil	Nil	Nil	yes
CGS Camotes	Nil	1- Svc	Nil	Nil	Nil	Nil	yes
CGS Negros Oriental	1- Svc	2- Svc 1- Usvc	Nil	Nil	Nil	Nil	Nil

Units/ Stations	Search and Rescue Vessel (SARV)	Multi Role Response Vessel	Diesel Fast Craft (DF)	Communi- cation Equipme nt	Standby Rescue Plane	Standby Helicopters	Unmanned Remote Underwater Vehicle
CGS Central Cebu	Nil	Nil	Nil	yes	Nil	Nil	Nil
CGS Western Bohol	Nil	Nil	Nil	yes	Nil	Nil	Nil
CGS Eastern Bohol	Nil	Nil	Nil	yes	Nil	Nil	Nil
CGS Northern Cebu	Nil	Nil	Nil	yes	Nil	Nil	Nil
CGS Southern Cebu	Nil	Nil	Nil	yes	Nil	Nil	Nil
CGS Siquijor	Nil	Nil	Nil	yes	Nil	Nil	Nil
CGS Camotes	Nil	Nil	Nil	yes	Nil	Nil	Nil
CGS Negros Oriental	Nil	Nil	Nil	yes	Nil	Nil	Nil
HCDCV	Nil	1-Svc	1-Usv	yes	Nil	Nil	Nil

*Legend: Svc - Serviceable
Usvc – Unserviceable*

*Nil- None
Yes- has adequate supply*

In Table 15, the findings revealed the following major challenges encountered by Coast Guard District Central Visayas in Performing Maritime Search and Rescue Operations in terms of the PCG Assets:

1. Most stations have no issuance of Rubber Boats in their stations/ Sub-stations.
2. No issuance of Unmanned Aerial Vehicle (UAV) or drones and Unmanned Underwater Vehicle (UUV) use for SAR operations.
3. No Provision of ambulance.
4. Non-Issuance of Unmanned Aerial Vehicle (UAV) or drones use for SAR operation.
5. No provision of Rigid Hull Inflatable Boats to stations.
6. Most stations don't have standby PCG Search and Rescue Vessel or Multi Role Response Vessel deployed for SAR operations.
7. Most stations have no issuance of Rubber Boats in their stations/ Sub-stations

Most stations have no issuance of Rubber Boats in their stations/ Sub-stations. The limitations in PCG assets that the Coast Guard District Central Visayas encounters while conducting maritime search and rescue (SAR) operations are consistent with the worldwide problems about insufficient resources in maritime safety organizations. The lack of crucial resources such as backup aircraft, unmanned underwater vehicles, and ambulances, as mentioned in Table 15, greatly impairs the

efficiency and effectiveness of search and rescue operations. These limits align with the results of research conducted internationally. According to Miętkiewicz (2023), the absence of sophisticated technology resources, such as UAVs and UUVs, limits the capacity of maritime organizations to carry out comprehensive and prompt search operations. In addition, the lack of essential equipment, such as rigid hull inflatable boats, significantly limits operational capabilities. Brunet (2022) emphasizes that sufficient and specialized equipment is crucial for the effectiveness of search and rescue missions. The lack of essential medical equipment and first aid supplies presents significant dangers to the safety of both rescuers and victims. This highlights the importance of allocating resources comprehensively to improve operational preparedness and response effectiveness (Ben-Noun, 2023). Hence, it is imperative to tackle these asset-related obstacles to enhance the overall search and rescue (SAR) capability of the Coast Guard District Central Visayas.

Challenges of Coast Guard District Central Visayas In Performing Maritime Search and Rescue Operations in Terms of Policies and Standard Operating Procedures

The researcher conducted document review of the existing Philippine Coast Guard (PCG) policies and standard operating procedures for PCG units in the conduct of Search and Rescue (SAR). The researcher contacted the Station Commanders of Coast Guard District Central Visayas and ask if there are existing policies that their Stations are using in relation to the conduct of SAR operations. Accordingly, they are using the PCG SAR Manual series of 2011 as its guide/ reference in the conduct of SAR operations in their area of responsibility. The researcher interviewed the Station Commanders of CGDCV and checked if other than the PCG SAR Manual if there are other existing SAR related policies that they are using as reference and accordingly they don't have any other than the mentioned PCG SAR manual. The researcher conducted cross checking and validation to the Higher Headquarters in Manila by interviewing the Commanding Officer of the Coast Guard Search and Rescue Unit under Maritime Safety Services Command and confirmed that aside from the PCG SAR manual they don't have any updated SAR policies and that they still crafting a Memorandum Circular policy regarding SAR.

Further, the documentary review revealed that in the Implementation and monitoring of maritime incidents prior conducting SAR operations, the PCG has a standardized format of reporting and monitoring, to include the dissemination of information's and strictly follows the chain of command. The PCG SAR manual also contains the standard procedures in conducting SAR operations and different search patterns commonly used internationally. The researcher believes that to have an effective and efficient in SAR responses there must be a clear and updated policies that can upkeep in the present time depending on the different situations that may arise. The researcher also believes that the policies and procedure in SAR operations should be always be updated in comparable to the current situation in advent of the introduction of new SAR technologies and the effects of climate change.

Furthermore, the absence of standardized operating procedures (SOPs) for different situations highlights the difficulties identified by Gavel et al., (2021), who assert that

SOPs are essential for efficiently organizing search and rescue efforts and maintaining uniformity in response tactics. In addition, there are concerns about obsolete policies, ineffective dissemination, and awareness initiatives that align with broader discussions in the literature emphasizing the importance of conducting regular policy reviews and implementing improved communication methods within search and rescue (SAR) organizations. It is crucial to address these challenges in order to improve the effectiveness and efficiency of search and rescue (SAR) operations.

Conclusions

In view of the findings of the study, the following conclusion was drawn:

1.The demographic and professional characteristics analysis provides a strong foundation for understanding the Coast Guard District Central Visayas' workforce composition and readiness for maritime search and rescue operations. By leveraging the strengths identified in age diversity, educational attainment, rank distribution, and comprehensive training programs, the Coast Guard is poised to strengthen its operational capabilities and effectively respond to maritime emergencies in the Central Visayas region. Continued emphasis on professional development and strategic deployment will further enhance organizational resilience and readiness, ensuring maritime safety and security in the area.

2.Based on the findings, the Coast Guard personnel's readiness, proactive decision-making, and effective utilization of resources across different distress scenarios. Their strategic approach ensures swift deployment of assets, coordination with relevant authorities, and utilization of specialized assistance, enhancing the overall effectiveness of response and rescue operations in the Central Visayas region. Looking forward, continued emphasis on training, scenario-based drills, and inter-agency coordination will further strengthen the Coast Guard District Central Visayas' capabilities in maritime search and rescue operations. Leveraging these strengths and addressing identified areas for enhancement, the Coast Guard is well-positioned to uphold maritime safety, respond effectively to emergencies, and safeguard maritime interests in the Central Visayas district and beyond.

3.Based on the findings hypotheses of no correlation are rejected for each case due to the computed t-values exceeding the critical t-value at a significance level of 0.05. This indicates that there are indeed significant relationships between age, gender, rank, highest educational attainment, years of service, current assignment/station, trainings attended, and performance assessments among Coast Guard personnel in the Central Visayas district.

4.Addressing challenges through strategic interventions in personnel development, training enhancement, operational optimization, asset provisioning, and policy refinement, Coast Guard District Central Visayas can enhance its capability to effectively conduct maritime search and rescue operations. These efforts will foster greater operational efficiency, resilience, and responsiveness, thereby reinforcing the

organization's commitment to safeguarding maritime interests and responding effectively to emergencies in the region and beyond.

Recommendations

In view of the findings of the study the following recommendations are being suggested:

1.The researcher recommended a structured action plan to address challenges in maritime search and rescue operations. The plan includes enhancing personnel capability, improving training programs, optimizing operational strategies, and allocating resources. The plan emphasizes proactive measures to uphold maritime safety and security, ensuring the district's commitment to safeguarding maritime interests and enhancing emergency response capabilities. The plan aims to achieve measurable enhancements in operational readiness and response efficiency.

2.To address the identified challenges in personnel capability within the Coast Guard District Central Visayas, several key initiatives are recommended. Firstly, there is a crucial need to ensure an adequate number of qualified maintenance personnel. This can be achieved through targeted recruitment drives aimed at attracting individuals with specialized skills essential for maintaining and repairing fleet assets. Additionally, implementing comprehensive training programs focused on skill enhancement is essential. These programs should not only improve technical proficiency but also boost personnel confidence in handling diverse maritime emergencies effectively. Furthermore, it is imperative to provide proper equipment, tools, and materials that are well-maintained and readily accessible to support seamless operations during rescue missions.

3.Enhancing the Coast Guard's training framework is vital for improving operational readiness and response effectiveness. It is recommended to develop and implement comprehensive training programs that cover both theoretical knowledge and practical skills relevant to maritime search and rescue operations. These programs should incorporate advanced training delivery methods, making use of interactive and scenario-based approaches that simulate real-world emergencies. Moreover, expanding training opportunities through international partnerships, virtual training sessions, and skills enhancement workshops will ensure continuous professional development among Coast Guard personnel.

4.To optimize operational effectiveness, strategies should focus on enhancing readiness, coordination, and search capabilities. Regular drills, scenario-based exercises, and simulations are essential to improve operational readiness and ensure personnel are well-prepared for emergencies. Strengthening coordination mechanisms with local and international partners will facilitate seamless collaboration during rescue operations. Additionally, investing in advanced technologies such as UAVs, UUVs, satellite imaging, and advanced communication systems will enhance the Coast Guard's search capabilities and response efficiency.

5.Modernizing the Coast Guard fleet is critical for maintaining operational superiority. This involves prioritizing the acquisition of new vessels equipped with state-of-the-art navigation, communication, and rescue equipment. Implementing a rigorous maintenance schedule is equally important to ensure all fleet assets are in optimal

operational condition at all times. Furthermore, allocating resources for researching and adopting new technologies will further enhance operational efficiency, safety, and response capabilities during maritime emergencies.

6. Developing clear policies, guidelines, and standardized operating procedures (SOPs) is essential for ensuring consistency and effectiveness in maritime search and rescue operations. Regular reviews and updates of existing policies should be conducted to address current challenges and align with international best practices. Establishing SOPs that outline precise protocols for response, communication, coordination, and decision-making during emergencies will enhance operational efficiency and safety. Effective implementation of SOPs should be ensured through continuous training, drills, and evaluations, thereby increasing awareness among personnel about their importance in enhancing operational readiness and safety.

7. Future research should focus on the long-term impact of age and experience on performance in maritime search and rescue teams, explore gender dynamics in Coast Guard operations, integrate emerging technologies like AI and machine learning, and study climate change resilience in maritime safety and emergency response strategies. These studies aim to understand generational shifts, gender dynamics, and the effectiveness of adaptation measures in diverse environmental conditions.

Compliance with Ethical Standards

This study adhered to ethical standards, obtaining informed consent from all participants and ensuring their right to withdraw at any time. Anonymity and confidentiality were maintained to protect privacy, and personal identifiers were removed or coded. The well-being of the respondents was a primary concern, and procedures were conducted with respect for their rights and dignity. No conflict of interest existed, and plagiarism was avoided by properly citing sources and acknowledging previous research contributions. Bias in the interpretation of findings was meticulously avoided. Objective data analysis techniques and rigorous methodological standards were employed to ensure the validity and reliability of the results. The findings and conclusions were used for academic and research purposes, contributing to maritime training and safety knowledge.

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